

Acylation Reactions of some Chelated *o*-Hydroxy Aldoxime*

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Acylation of bis(salicylaldoximate)copper(II), bis(5-nitrosalicylaldoximate)copper(II), bis(5-bromosalicylaldoximate)copper(II), bis(5-nitro- β -resorcyalaldoximate)copper(II) and bis(2-hydroxy-1-naphthaldoximate)copper(II) with acetic anhydride, *n*-propionic anhydride, *n*-butyric anhydride and valeric anhydride gave respective oximinoacylaldoxime chelates. In case of 5-nitro- β -resorcyalaldoxime chelate the phenolic hydroxyl remain unreacted. The chelates were characterised from their elemental analysis and infrared spectra.

PREVIOUS work from this laboratory has reported on the reactivity of chelated salicylaldoxime¹ and β -resorcyalaldoxime². As a part of our general programme of work on the reactivity of coordinated ligands, we have recently carried out the acylation reactions of some *o*-hydroxyaloximes chelated to copper(II), the results of the investigations being presented here. For the first time, successful *n*-propylation, *n*-butyrylation, and valerylation of chelated oximes have been achieved.

Experimental

Acetic, *n*-propionic and *n*-butyric anhydrides used were of laboratory reagents quality (B.D.H.). Other anhydrides were of pure grade (Fluka). All the anhydrides, except benzoic anhydride, were distilled over phosphorus pentoxide before use. All the parent copper(II) chelates were synthesized from the reactions of ligands with copper acetate and their purity was checked by elemental analysis.

Acylation reactions :

For the acylation reactions, the chelates were treated with excess of acid anhydrides, till the completion of the reaction. The suspension obtained in each case was filtered and the solid collected, after washing with pure and dry carbon tetrachloride till free from the acid and the acid anhydride, was dried under vacuum. The quantities of reactants, reaction temperature, reaction time, product obtained and its analysis in each case have been given in Table I.

Infrared spectra of the compounds in Nujol mull were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer infracord spectrophotometer Model 137E, using sodium chloride prism. NMR spectra of the ligands were recorded on a Varian Associates Model A-60 spectrometer operating at 60 Mc/s, with TMS as internal standard.

Results and Discussion

All the parent chelates showed a strong and sharp band in the region 3200-3400 cm^{-1} in the infrared spectra, which can be ascribed to the oximino hydroxyl group. The absence of the band due to OH stretching vibrations in the infrared spectra of the acylated products (except 5-nitro- β -resorcyalaldoximate product where the intensity of the OH signal was reduced) and appearance of a new band in the region 1700-1800 cm^{-1} , ascribable to C=O stretching vibration indicated acylation through the replacement of the hydrogen atom in the oxime hydroxyl group². That the phenolic hydroxyl group, in the case of 5-nitro- β -resorcyalaldoximate chelate remains unaffected during acetylation was confirmed by our experiments which failed to acylate the bis(5-nitro- β -resorcyalaldehyde)copper(II) chelate under conditions used for the corresponding aldoximate chelate and yielded back the parent chelate. All the acylated chelates gave back the parent chelates on hydrolysis with water or alkali.

The time of acylation reactions for a particular chelate increased with the chain length of the anhydrides, which is justified on the basis of inductive effect. It may be noted that the resacetophenoxime chelate of copper(II) decomposed during acylation whereas the 5-nitroresacetophenoxime copper(II) chelate could be acetylated indicating that the nitrosubstituent increases the stability of the complex.

Attempts to acylate the chelates with acid chloride did not succeed apparently due to the decomposition of the products (indicated by the formation of cupric chloride) by the hydrochloric acid formed in the reaction. This suggests the acid anhydrides to be the selective acylating agents for these complexes.

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TABLE I

Sl. No.	Reactants		Reaction temp. °C	Reaction time	Name of the product obtained and formula	Colour	Yield %	Analysis %		
	Copper chelate	Acid anhydride in ml.						C	H	Cu
1.	Bis(salicylaldoximate)copper(II) [0.84 g; 0.0025 mole]	<i>n</i> -Propionic anhydride, 15 ml.	30	40 min.	Bis(oximino- <i>n</i> -propyl-salicylaldoximate)copper(II) C ₂₀ H ₂₀ N ₂ O ₆ Cu	Brown	1.05 g. (93.8)	53.8 (53.6)	4.61 (4.50)	14.3 (14.2)
2.	-do-	<i>n</i> -Butyric anhydride 15 ml.	30	1.5 hrs.	Bis(oximino- <i>n</i> -butyryl-salicylaldoximate)copper(II) C ₂₂ H ₂₄ N ₂ O ₆ Cu	Dark green	1.05 g. (88.2)	55.3 (55.5)	5.16 (5.08)	13.1 (13.4)
3.	-do-	Valeric anhydride	30	3.0 hrs.	Bis(oximinovaleeryl-salicylaldoximate)copper(II) C ₂₄ H ₂₆ N ₂ O ₆ Cu	Brown	0.70 g. (55.5)	56.7 (57.2)	5.55 (5.60)	12.5 (12.6)
4.	-do-	Benzoic anhydride 1.13 g; 0.005 mole in 25 ml. chloroform	30	2.0 hrs.	Bis(oximinobenzoyl-salicylaldoximate)copper(II) C ₂₆ H ₂₀ N ₂ O ₆ Cu	Green	1.20 g. (38.2)	61.2 (61.9)	3.90 (3.70)	11.9 (11.7)
5.	Bis(5-bromosalicylaldoximate)copper(II) [1.23 g; 0.0025 mole]	Acetic anhydride 15 ml.	30	20 min.	Bis(oximinocetyl-5-bromo-salicylaldoximate)copper(II) C ₁₈ H ₁₄ O ₆ Br ₂ N ₂ Cu	Brown	1.35 g. (93.5)	37.4 (37.4)	2.51 (2.44)	11.0 (11.0)
6.	-do-	<i>n</i> -Propionic anhydride 15 ml.	30	30 min.	Bis(oximino- <i>n</i> -propyl-5-bromo-salicylaldoximate)copper(II) C ₂₀ H ₁₈ N ₂ Br ₂ O ₆ Cu	Pale yellow	1.45 g. (95.8)	39.7 (39.8)	3.34 (3.00)	10.3 (10.5)
7.	-do-	<i>n</i> -Butyric anhydride 15 ml.	30	4.5 hrs.	Bis(oximino- <i>n</i> -butyryl-5-bromosalicylaldoximate)-copper(II) C ₂₂ H ₂₂ N ₂ Br ₂ O ₆ Cu	Brownish yellow	1.45 g. (91.5)	41.6 (41.7)	3.71 (3.50)	10.2 (10.1)
8.	Bis(5-bromosalicylaldoximate)copper(II) [1.23 g; 0.0025 mole]	Valeric anhydride 15 ml.	30	7.0 hrs.	Bis(oximinovaleeryl-5-bromo-salicylaldoximate)Copper(II) C ₂₄ H ₂₆ N ₂ Br ₂ O ₆ Cu	Brown	1.50 g. (90.6)	43.0 (43.6)	4.19 (3.96)	9.41 (9.27)
9.	Bis(5-nitrosalicylaldoximate)copper(II) [1.07 g; 0.0025 mole]	Acetic anhydride 15 ml.	65—70	30 min.	Bis(oximinocetyl-5-nitro-salicylaldoximate)copper(II) C ₁₈ H ₁₄ N ₄ O ₁₀ Cu	Green	1.10 g. (86.3)	43.0 (42.4)	3.06 (2.77)	12.1 (12.6)
10.	-do-	<i>n</i> -Propionic anhydride 15 ml.	90—95	30 min.	Bis(oximino- <i>n</i> -propyl-5-nitrosalicylaldoximate)-copper(II) C ₂₀ H ₁₈ N ₄ O ₁₀ Cu	Dirty green	1.20 g. (89.2)	45.1 (44.7)	3.69 (3.37)	11.9 (11.8)
11.	-do-	<i>n</i> -Butyric anhydride 15 ml.	90—95	90 min.	Bis(oximino- <i>n</i> -butyryl-5-nitro-salicylaldoximate)copper(II) C ₂₂ H ₂₂ N ₄ O ₁₀ Cu	Green	1.10 g. (77.7)	46.9 (46.7)	4.12 (3.92)	11.3 (11.2)

TABLE I Contd.

Sl. No.	Reactants		Reaction temp. °C	Reaction time	Name of the product obtained and formula	Colour	Yield %	Analysis %		
	copper chelate	Acid anhydride in ml.						C	H	Cu
12.	-do-	Valeric anhydride 15 ml.	90—95	3 hrs.	Bis(oximinovaleeryl-5-nitro-salicylaldoximate)copper(II) C ₂₄ H ₂₆ N ₄ O ₁₀ Cu	Green	1.25 g. (86.7)	48.5 (48.9)	4.13 (3.76)	10.6 (10.8)
13.	Bis(5-nitro-β-resorcyldoximate)copper(II) [1.15 g.; 0.0025 mole]	Acetic anhydride 15 ml.	90—95	40 min.	Bis(oximinooctyl-5-nitro-β-resorcyldoximate)copper(II) C ₁₈ H ₁₄ N ₄ O ₁₂ Cu	Dark dirty green	1.25 g. (92.3)	40.6 (39.9)	2.13 (2.61)	11.3 (11.7)
14.	-do-	n-Propionic anhydride 15 ml.	90—95	1.0 hr.	Bis(oximino-n-propyl-5-nitro-β-resorcyldoximate)copper(II) C ₂₀ H ₁₆ N ₄ O ₁₂ Cu	Greenish yellow	1.35 g. (94.7)	42.5 (42.2)	3.38 (3.18)	11.3 (11.2)
15.	Bis(5-nitro-β-resorcyldoximate)copper(II) [1.15 g.; 0.0025 mole]	n-Butyric anhydride 15 ml.	90—95	2 hrs.	Bis(oximino-n-butyryl-5-nitro-β-resorcyldoximate)copper(II) C ₂₂ H ₂₂ N ₄ O ₁₂ Cu	Green	1.25 g. (83.6)	43.5 (44.2)	4.07 (3.71)	10.5 (10.6)
16.	-do-	Valeric anhydride 15 ml.	"	5 hrs.	Bis(oximinovaleeryl-5-nitro-β-resorcyldoximate)copper(II) C ₂₄ H ₂₆ N ₄ O ₁₂ Cu	Green	1.35 g. (86.2)	45.9 (46.1)	4.27 (4.19)	10.2 (10.2)
17.	Bis(2-hydroxy-1-naphthaldoximate)copper(II) [1.09 g.; 0.0025 mole]	Acetic anhydride 15 ml.	65—70	30 min.	Bis(oximinooctyl-2-hydroxy-1-naphthaldoximate)copper(II) C ₂₆ H ₂₀ N ₂ O ₆ Cu	Dark brown	1.10 g. (84.6)	60.2 (60.1)	4.16 (3.88)	12.1 (12.2)
18.	-do-	n-Propionic anhydride 15 ml.	90—95	20 min.	Bis(oximino-n-propyl-2-hydroxy-1-naphthaldoximate)copper(II) C ₂₈ H ₂₄ N ₂ O ₆ Cu	-do-	1.25 g. (94.2)	61.6 (61.4)	4.71 (4.71)	11.5 (11.6)
19.	-do-*	n-Butyric anhydride 15 ml.	-do-	30 min.	Bis(oximino-n-butyryl-2-hydroxy-1-naphthaldoximate)copper(II) C ₃₀ H ₂₈ N ₂ O ₆ Cu	Brown needles	0.95 g. (66.0)	62.3 (62.6)	5.05 (4.90)	11.2 (11.0)
20.	-do-	Valeric anhydride 15 ml.	-do-	90 min.	Bis(oximinovaleeryl-2-hydroxy-1-naphthaldoximate)copper(II) C ₃₂ H ₂₂ N ₂ O ₆ Cu	Brown	1.20 g. (79.5)	63.8 (63.6)	5.30 (5.34)	10.4 (10.5)
21.	Bis(5-nitroresacetophenoximate)copper(II) [1.22 g.; 0.0025 mole]	Acetic anhydride 15 ml.	65—70	30 min.	Bis(oximinooctyl-5-nitro-resacetophenoximate)copper(II) C ₂₀ H ₁₈ N ₄ O ₁₂ Cu	Green	0.40 g. (28.0)	42.7 (42.2)	3.41 (3.18)	11.2 (11.2)

* This compound dissolved in acid anhydride in about 30 minutes and bis(oximino-n-butyryl-2-hydroxy-1-naphthaldoximate)copper(II) separated out from the solution with cooling with ice-cold water.

Required values of analysis are given in parenthesis.

References

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